

THE ROLE OF STRINGED INSTRUMENTS IN UZBEK FOLK MUSIC

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Abstract: This article talks about the role of stringed instruments in the creation of Uzbek folk music, their history, diversity and their uniqueness in folk music.

Key words: Uzbek folk music, concertmaster, soloist, stringed instruments, oud, tanbur, dutor, rubob, sato,

Uzbek folk instruments were formed in the bosom of ancient eastern culture. They have preserved their unique characteristics and tone during centuries of development. Due to their unique structure, chang, flute, trumpet, tanbur, dutor, rubob, gijjak, kobiz have reached us in traditional forms. Stringed instruments have a long history in the creation of Uzbek folk music. The emergence and development of these instruments is closely related to cultural exchanges and trade routes in the Central Asian regions. Over the centuries, these instruments have been enriched by various international and regional influences.

Uzbek folk music has various stringed instruments. Some of them are:

Oud, tanbur, rubob are the leading musical instruments of Muslims. In the musical treatises of the past, the theoretical and practical foundations of the chord structures of classical music are explained using the sound system of the oud and tanbur instruments.

The name of the world-famous oud instrument is related to the unique oud (shamshod) tree from which it is made (from which medicinal and aromatic substances are extracted). The history of the origin of the sound known as oud in Muslim countries, piypo in China, and lyutnya in Europe (from the Arabic word "al-ud") began to develop long before the emergence of Islam.

Ud - a classical musical instrument with strings and mizrob. It is widely used in Arab, Turkish, Persian, Caucasian (Azerbaijani, Armenian) and Central Asian (Uzbek, Tajik) peoples. A large, pear-shaped calyx with a thin lid and a short, wide handle. The sound is soft and mellow. It is known that the oud originally had 4 strings, and 5 strings were added by a musician named Ziriyob (9th century) (Farobi in some sources). The currently used Oud is fretless and has 11 strings. 5 of them are double strings, the bottom string is single. Oud is

mainly used as an accompaniment (classical music ensembles) and as a solo instrument.

Tanbur is one of the louder instruments used by professional musicians, and the carved bowl is made of solid mulberry wood along with a thick and long handle; general 110-130 cm. The lid of the bowl is usually made of a thin wooden board with resonator holes. There are 16-19 frets tied with a string, and the sixth is usually moved up or down depending on the tonality of the piece being played. On the lid of the cup there will be 4 more special curtains made of wood. The first of the 3 strings of the tanbur (from the top) is the main one, 2 are auxiliary; the first and third are tuned in unison, and the second is tuned a fourth, sometimes a fifth or a second lower than them. The tanbur is played in different ways (by hitting the strings from above and below) with a nail worn on the index finger of the hand. Unlike other stringed percussion instruments in Uzbekistan, the tanbur has a diatonic tone. Since the strings of the tanbur are long and thin, and the curtains are thick (up to 3 mm in diameter), it is possible to change the pitch of the sound up to a semitone by pressing the string with different force. In this way, the tunes in the tanbur are given a unique vibration, polish, and laments. due to its unique delicate and impressive sound and wide range, the tanbur is the main soloist and (in vocal parts) accompanying instrument in the performance of maqam.

There are different interpretations about the etymological meaning of the word "Tanbur". According to one of them, it consists of two roots: "tan" and "bur". "Tan" means the body, and "bur" is the imperative verb of "buridan" - "to cut". Usually this word is explained as meaning "heart-scratcher". According to another assumption stated in Professor Fitrat's book "Uzbek classical music and its history", "tanbur" is a modified form of the currently known Uzbek musical instrument - dombira.

Although dombira and tanbur were very closely related to each other in the early stages of their formation, their paths diverged due to their later destiny due to their conformity to different musical traditions. Currently, the Uzbek drum has become an instrument related to the art of bakhshi. In this case, it is used only in the performance of epics and terms (song couplets of a plotless nature) in the style of "inner voice" (a kind of throat singing).

In his thoughts on the history of the tanbur, Fitrat writes that some Shayban musician Mahmud added a third string to it, and this instrument became a "setor" (three strings). In connection with Setor, it is necessary to mention another name of tanbur - "sato". Even today, Uzbek musicians play the tanbur

with a bow, calling it "sato" and classifying it as an independent instrument. Sato is, of course, nothing more than the Uyghur pronunciation of the word "setor".

From the point of view of acoustic aspects, the soft and pleasant sounds of the tanbur are similar to the broad tenor voice emanating from the chest. tanbur incorporates all the necessary sound capabilities to implement the extremely complex lad system of maqams. It is not for nothing that Tanbur is considered the key to the Shashmaqom curtain system. Three- and four-string types of tanburs are used in maqam musical instruments. According to teachers, a three-stringed tanbur is suitable and convenient for accompanying a song, and a four-stringed one is suitable for playing the instrument.

The tanbur sound range covers a range of about three octaves: from the small octave "sol" to the third octave "mi" - "fa". This is the actual range of the Shashmaqom curtain system, filled with the sound field of that highly specialized singing and special peaks such as Turk, Zebo pari, Muhayyar. The perfection of the tanbur is that it sounds evenly in all places (layers - registers) in this wide volume.

Dutor is one of the ancient musical instruments, which looks like a drum, but is fundamentally different from it with its performance capabilities and visual means, and is played not only by amateur folk performers, but also by skilled professional musicians. The Noximoi bowl is carved or ribbed, and a thin lid is attached to a relatively long and thin handle attached to it. On the relatively long handle installed in the bowl, there are curtains tied in two coils of twine or silk strings. Typically, there are 13 frets, which create a full non-chromatic sound range with a range of more than two octaves. The dutor's two silk strings are tuned to quarta, fifth, or unison (octave). The main method of performance in dutor is the scratch, as in dombira. At the same time, dutor is distinguished by the richness of strokes used, the variety of styles of using the fingers of the right hand and the paw.

Before that, the main instrument and "key" of Khorezm classical music was dutor. Dutor is a musical instrument that sounds like "house" (chamber) by nature. We can say that all of its qualities are correct: gently playing with the fingertip, or rather, making a sound by gently "stroking" the delicate sounding silk strings with the hand. Tanbur is an instrument with a more open and bright sound compared to dutor.

Afghan rubobi (also known as Bukhara or Tajik rubobi) is a percussion instrument with a unique shape. A large and deep carving covered with leather. a thin cover is glued to the top of the narrowed sides of the body. Usually, only 4

parts of the intestine are tied to the thick handle, which is one whole with the body, and the wooden caps are glued to the wooden cover of the rest. Typically, a rubab has 5 playable main strings (including 1-2, 3-4 double strings tuned in unison) and 10-11 resonating strings that are drawn to the side ears. , while the main resonant strings are tuned in fourths, while the resonant strings form step-ascending seconds. Despite the fact that the range is within two octaves, the Afghan ruby is used by almost professional folk musicians in solo and ensemble compositions in Uzbekistan, mainly in the city of Bukhara.

The end of the 40s and the beginning of the 50s of the 20th century coincided with the introduction of a new direction of performance in folk musical instruments in the field of public education. More European, Russian and Uzbek composers teach Uzbek national musical instruments (tanbur, dutor, gijjak, nay, chang, etc.) in primary, secondary and higher education systems. performing his works was the first priority. In this process, the kashgar rubobi became one of the most widely used national instruments.

Kashkar rubobi - a semi-circular round carved bowl, the top of which is covered with leather, and two wooden branches protruding from the sides of its thick and long handle are a characteristic feature of this instrument. is thrown into z. The strings of the Kashkar rubobi are five in number: three are made of silk (or cotton), two are made of wire (nowadays, they are all made of wire of different thicknesses). They are adjusted to quarta-quinta. 19-23 thin strings are attached to the handle of the rubob, which creates a full chromatic sound line of three octaves (now, almost all of them have metal clips attached to the top of the handle). It is played like an Afghan rubobi with a simple mediator (nokhunak). Rubob occupies a special place among Uzbek national musical instruments. It is widely used in traditional and modern Uzbek music, and its importance is distinguished in several ways. Rubab is an integral part of the rich musical heritage of the Uzbek people. This musical instrument has played an important role in folk music, epics and hymns for centuries. It helps to preserve ancient traditions and customs. Rubob has a unique sound and a wide range, and can be played in different genres and styles. It is used both in classical and folk music and in modern arrangements. Rubab is one of the main musical instruments in maqam art. Makams are distinguished by their complex rhythmic and melodic structures, and the rubab plays an important role in the precise and subtle performance of this musical system. Rubob performers are often regarded as ambassadors of art and culture. They present Uzbek music at various festivals and international events, thereby introducing Uzbek culture to the world. Rubob

is a valuable musical instrument that has not only historical and cultural significance in Uzbek music, but also has its place in the modern music scene. Stringed instruments play an important role in Uzbek folk music. They not only define the rhythm and tone of the music, but also express the spirit and content of the music. With the help of these instruments, performers express their feelings, pains and joys. Also, stringed instruments show the richness and variety of Uzbek folk music.

Today, a lot of work is being done on the study and preservation of string instruments. Special courses on these instruments are organized in music schools and conservatories. Popularization of these instruments is also ensured through folk art festivals and events.

Summary:

In conclusion, we can say that stringed instruments play an important role in the creation of Uzbek folk music. Their history, variety, and role in folk music make these instruments unique and valuable. These instruments remain an integral part of Uzbek folk music not only in the past, but also today and are passed on to future generations. The rich cultural heritage of stringed instruments testifies to the high and rich music art of Uzbekistan.

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